

Fluctuation of ecological niches and geographic range shifts along chile pepper's domestication gradient.

– ODMAP Protocol –

2023-09-30

Overview

Authorship

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Study link: DOI: 10.1002/ece3.10731

Model objective

Model objective: Forecast and transfer

Target output: Suitable vs unsuitable habitat for each domestication category, their overlap and their differences under present conditions and under future climate change scenarios.

Focal Taxon

Focal Taxon: Wild chili pepper (*Capsicum annuum* var. *glabriusculum*) and domesticated chili pepper (*Capsicum annuum* var. *annuum*)

Location

Location: Mexico

Scale of Analysis

Spatial extent: -124, -65.374, 6.833, 40 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)

Spatial resolution: 2.5 arc minutes

Temporal extent: <50 records from (1887, 1920, 1932, 1933, 1935, 1938-1940, 1942, 1948, 1956, 1957, 1959, 1964, 1967-1969), >4000 records from (1970-2004, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2013-2015, 2018-2019).

Temporal resolution: present, and projections for 2040-2060, 2060-2080 and 2080-2100 intervals

Boundary: rectangle

Biodiversity data

Observation type: field survey

Response data type: point occurrence, presence-only

Predictors

Predictor types: climatic

Hypotheses

Hypotheses: The domestication gradient (as a proxy of the domestication process) shows evidence of an anthropogenic expansion of *Capsicum annuum*'s ecological niche in the environmental and geographical realms. Under climate change scenarios, wild populations could have more severe restrictions in their projected distributions due to the lack of agricultural management's buffering effect.

Assumptions

Model assumptions: * Climate is a relevant ecological driver of this species distribution. * Correlation among predictor variables does not change drastically in future climate scenarios. * The species distribution is in pseudo-equilibrium with their environment, that is, it may be described by a static distribution model where the observed response depends on the environmental conditions. * Wild and cultivated niches may be compared using the same explanatory variables. * Mexico-only sampling allows to compare among domestication phase yet may constitute an under-estimate of suitable conditions. * Sampling is representative in area, with biases and spatial auto-correlation accounted for or corrected when possible. * Sagarpa irrigation and rain-fed polygons' random points are an accurate proxy of cultivated chili pepper localities. * The domestication process led to the species' niche evolution to encompass areas different from wild plants' environmental envelope partly through human management, whereas we rely on niche conservatism within each domestication category to project these models into future climate. * Wild chili pepper's niche was not significantly modified by the advent of domestication, although it might have been displaced from some of the areas it used to occupy (under-canopy replaced by open fields).

Algorithms

Modelling techniques: maxent

Model complexity: We tested different combinations of feature classes and beta-multiplier parameters for each data set, and scored AICc and Average test AUC. We selected a fixed set of feature classes over data sets and varied the complexity penalization beta-multiplier value accordingly. Such tests were run on spatially partitioned data (checkerboard pattern), yet results were highly similar when not including this, so final models were run using random test points. Clamping was used to counteract our Mexico-only sampling and thus avoid overprojection. Models were additionally scored through true skill statistic values (TSS).

Model averaging: none, future models per RCP and year were overlapped and pixels colored according to number of coincident models

Workflow

Model workflow: Occurrence data was processed and formatted for each domestication group. Occurrence points were classified as Wild, Semiwild, Landrace or Commercial subsets. (Note that codes will refer to semiwilds or arvense as synonyms). Wild category was defined to occur in natural habitats and exhibit wild phenotypic behavior without signs of chile pepper domestication syndrome. Semiwilds were characterized as semiwild plants that may occur in human-managed spaces such as back-yards, small family plots or milpa agroecosystems, where they grow spontaneously and are tolerated/consumed yet retain a wild-like phenotype. Landraces are identified as such by farmers and communities and are typically grown through traditional agriculture with a tendency to pertain to particular cultural regions in association to specific uses by local communities. Commercials represent cohesive and standardized varieties that are usually grown at large scales through high-input technology -dependent agriculture. Additional broad domestication groups merged Wild and Semiwild as "Wild sensu lato" and Landrace with Commercial as "Cultivated". Climate (19 bioclim variables at 2.5 arc-min), soil and slope/aspect values were extracted for all data points. Exceptionally the values of a few occurrences (>50 and >250) were imputed for variables: texture and slope-aspect respectively.

For exploratory PCA:

Correlation plots and PCA tables for variable contribution, loadings and coordinates were obtained for all data points as well as subsets of data points. Different variable combinations were tested to choose the most informative and low-correlated set of variables through expert knowledge of the biology of the system under study. With the selected variables, we performed scans on PCAs for Mahalanobis outliers on the whole set of data points. Each domestication category was then outlined and afore-mentioned PCA tables obtained, as well as factor maps and projection of data points along the first two principal components. Convex hulls for each category were plotted and area calculated as well as all pairwise combinations hull area overlap, points in the overlap/non-overlap area and intersection values. Violin plots were generated for each category for each variable to show value dispersion.

For niche modeling:

All environmental layers were cropped to a custom box chosen as informative, based on our knowledge of geographic scope of chile pepper (*Capsicum annuum*). This area included all of Mexico, plus southern United States, Central America and northern tip of South America. Layers were also cropped into a minimum convex polygon that comprised all data points thinned at 5km and was buffered for three degrees.

Each domestication category dataset was thinned five independent times at 5km and the resulting mapped occurrences compared before running. ENMeval R-package was run with the maxent algorithm, as coded by the Wallace Ecological Modeling App, to select the best

combination of Feature Class and Regularization multiplier values per data set. Data was spatially partitioned using checkerboard2 spatial method (which includes fine and coarse-grain aggregation). Feature Class combinations tested were L, LQ, LQH and LQHP (standing for L=linear, Q=quadratic, H=hinge and P=product, respectively) and Regularization multiplier values tested were 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 and 3.5. Tuning results were plotted and compared within and among occurrence datasets. Attention was given to values obtained for corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), Omission Rate (OR) and average test Area Under the Curve (AUC).

The polygon-cropped layers of the variables previously selected in the PCA section were employed as input for Maxent modeling. Maxent runs were performed on spatially thinned datasets through command lines and included the following specifications. Feature class selected was LQHP for all datasets with beta multiplier set to 3 for Wild, Wild s.l., Semiwild and Landrace datasets and at a value of 1 for Commercial and Cultivated datasets. Clamping was included to account for the artificial sampling barrier we established by including only points within Mexico. We asked for 10,000 background points and 30% random test points. Maximum iterations were set at 500. Ten replicates were run with replicate type selected as crossvalidation. Jackknife tests were requested. Projections were calculated and plotted for the custom-square clipped layers. We selected logistic output format for our projections. Background predictions were logged for downstream True Skill Statistic (TSS) calculations for each mean model, which were high and reassuring. Mean AUC and ROC curves were inspected for the ten-replicate averaged models to ensure performance. We compared maxent's output for average permutation importance of variables among domestication categories through barplots and stacked plots.

We used ENMTools R-package to calculate pairwise niche similarity tests: Schoener's D, Warren-Hellinger's I and Spearman rank correlation. We assessed spatial bias of our different sampling strategies by generating spatial bias files buffered at 1 degree for each dataset and cropped the environmental rasters accordingly. Maxent runs on these files produced over-projections, indicating adequately spread sampling effort throughout study areas.

Each of the ten replicate models obtained per dataset was independently projected onto the following CMIP6 custom-square cropped future layers at 2.5 arc-min resolution using terminal commands. We used the averages of the temporal intervals for years 2041-2060, 2061-2080 and 2081-2100, under two shared socioeconomic pathways SSP, 2: "middle of the road" with representative concentration pathway (RCP) of 45 and 5: "fossil-fueled development" with RCP of 85. For each of the afore-mentioned combinations eight general circulation models were run (BCC-CSM2-MR, CNRM-CM6-1, CNRM-ESM2-1, CanESM5, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MIROC-ES2L, MIROC6 and MRI-ESM2-0). Mean, median and standard deviation ASCII files of maps were obtained for each set of ten replicate future projections in R.

Threshold maps for each present model median projection as well as all pairwise combinations were obtained by calculating a specific threshold for each data set. Sample predictions for all ten replicates were extracted to obtain the upper 10th quantile value of the distribution. Maps were plotted for each dataset with their respective thresholds as

well as pairwise combinations among datasets/domestication categories to visualize geographic projection overlap. The same principle was applied to compare present vs each of the future scenario projections (year, SSP, GCM) for a given dataset, as well as among pairwise dataset comparisons within each future combination. Within each domestication category, pixel overlap metrics (loss, gain and shift) were calculated for each future projection as compared their present projections. We calculated the intersection of all eight GCM models per year-ssp combination and visualized the resulting map's overlap with present-time for which we again calculated, pixel loss, gain as well as the amount of pixel overlap per pairwise domestication category comparison for present projections as well as future GCM intersected projections.

We calculated Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces (MESS) in R, for each dataset including present occurrence points values plus background points values for each future scenario, to assess the extent of environmental differences involved in the projection. We also performed MESS analyses for each future scenario on terminal, obtaining novel environments estimates and their novel limiting variables (those that are most novel at each pixel). We were interested in ensuring those areas predicted to shift were not strongly climatically dissimilar in the future projections, in order to make more confident interpretations.

Software

Software: maxent.jar Maximum Entropy Modeling of Species Geographic Distributions version 3.4.0 R version 4.0.2 (2020-06-22) Main R packages: "sp" version 1.4-4 "rgdal" Geospatial Data Abstraction Library version: 1.5-19 "raster" version 3.4-5 "FactoMineR" version 2.3 "corrplot" version 0.84 "factoInvestigate" version 1.7 "spThin" version 0.2.0 "ENMeval" Automated runs and evaluations of ecological niche models version 0.3.1 "dismo" Species distribution modeling version: 1.3-3 "ENMTools" version 1.0.5 "spatstat" version 1.64-1 "rgeos" version 0.5-5

Data and code availability:

<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.c2fqz61d9>

Data

Biodiversity data

Taxon names: *Capsicum annuum* var. *annuum* and *Capsicum annuum* var. *glabriusculum*

Taxonomic reference system: Order: Solanales, Family: Solanaceae, Gender: *Capsicum* L., Species: *annuum* L. Varieties: *annuum* and *glabriusculum*

Ecological level: populations, individuals

Data sources: * Red Mundial de Información sobre la Biodiversidad (REMIB) "The World Information Network on Biodiversity"

http://www.conabio.gob.mx/remib_ingles/doctos/remib_ing.html * Secretaría de Agricultura y Desarrollo Rural (SAGARPA) "Agriculture and Rural development Agency".
<http://www.agricultura.gob.mx/siap/cartografia> * National Herbarium "MEXU", Institute of Biology, National Autonomous University of Mexico.
<http://www.ib.unam.mx/botanica/herbario/> * Kraft et al., PNAS (2014). Supplementary table third page. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1308933111> * Khoury et al., Diversity and Distributions (2020). Supplementary table, first page. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13008> * Aguilar-Meléndez et al., American Journal of Botany (2009) <https://doi.org/10.3732/ajb.0800155> * González-Jara et al., PLoS ONE (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0028715> * Field trips throughout Mexico (2013-2015 and 2018-2019) on behalf of Mercer and Jardón labs. * Sistema Nacional de Información sobre Biodiversidad de México "National System for Information on Mexican Biodiversity" (SNIB) from the Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad "National Commission for the Knowledge and Use of Biodiversity" (CONABIO) *Capsicum annum* var. *glabriusculum* query. * Goettsch et al., Plants, People, Planet (2021) <https://nph.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ppp3.10225>

Sampling design: Bibliography, Herbarium and Remib data without sub-sampling. Field trips were sampled for areas with missing data and following farmers advice through contacts. Sagarpa data was sampled randomly within cultivation polygons.

Sample size: *Capsicum annum* var *annuum*: 3815 occurrences, thinned to 2527 occurrences. *Capsicum annum* var *glabriusculum*: 679 occurrences, thinned to 358 occurrences.

Clipping: * Minimum convex polygon of occurrences buffered at 3 degrees * Box to surround polygon and include southern United States, Mexico, Central America and northern tip of South America (-124, -65.374, 6.833, 40 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax))

Scaling: Each database was spatially thinned at 5km.

Cleaning: Few Mahalanobis outliers were detected by Principal Components Analyses, all of which were corroborated to be true data points.

Absence data: None included

Background data: Background data was taken from a Minimum Convex Polygon that included all occurrences and was buffered at 3 degrees

Errors and biases: Proxies of occurrence points were calculated taking random points within irrigated and non-irrigated cultivation polygons reported by SAGARPA to include chile peppers. These points, which were included in Cultivated, Commercial and Landrace varieties, are thus, proxies.

Data partitioning

Training data: For model training aiming to model running, data was spatially partitioned using checkerboard2 spatial method (which includes fine and coarse-grain aggregation).

Validation data: Cross-validation method. 30% random test points.

Test data: We did not employ truly independent data. Test data was obtained as random test points.

Predictor variables

Predictor variables: 9 WorldClim bioclimatic variables. BIO2 = Mean Diurnal Range (Mean of monthly (max temp - min temp)) BIO3 = Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) ($\times 100$) BIO4 = Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation $\times 100$) BIO5 = Max Temperature of Warmest Month BIO9 = Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter BIO14 = Precipitation of Driest Month BIO15 = Precipitation Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation) BIO18 = Precipitation of Warmest Quarter BIO19 = Precipitation of Coldest Quarter

Data sources: <https://www.worldclim.org/data/bioclim.html>

Spatial extent: -123.0417, -80.91667, 8.875, 38.70833 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)

Spatial resolution: 2.5 arc-minutes

Coordinate reference system: WGS84: EPSG code = 4326

Temporal extent: Present (average for the years 1970-2000)

Temporal resolution: Present

Dimension reduction: Original dimension reduction of variable set was performed through Pearson correlation plots to select low correlated variables further scrutinized through expert knowledge on the biology of the system. Correlation plots were run for each dataset as well as for the whole dataset. Equivalent patterns were retrieved.

Transfer data

Data sources: CMIP6 downscaled future climate projections.

https://www.worldclim.org/data/cmip6/cmip6_clim2.5m.html

Spatial extent: -124, -65.374, 6.833, 40 (xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax)

Spatial resolution: 2.5 arc-minutes

Temporal extent: Present (average for the years 1970-2000), and predictions for 2041-2060, 2061-2080 and 2081-2100.

Temporal resolution: Thirty and twenty year averages.

Models and scenarios: 8 General Circulation Models (GCMs): BCC-CSM2-MR, CNRM-CM6-1, CNRM-ESM2-1, CanESM5, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MIROC-ES2L, MIROC6, MRI-ESM2-0 Two Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs): 245 and 585

Data processing: Downloaded future climate CMIP6 data was already downscaled and calibrated (bias corrected) with WorldClim v2.1 as baseline climate.

Quantification of Novelty: We calculated Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces (MESS) in R, for each dataset including present occurrence points values plus background points values for each future scenario (total of 288), to assess the extent of environmental differences involved in the projection. We also performed MESS analyses for each future scenario on terminal (total of 48), obtaining novel environments estimates and their novel limiting variables (those that are most novel at each pixel). Data visualization was performed through .asc and .png maps.

Model

Variable pre-selection

Variable pre-selection: Only climate variables were included because there are no available future soil layers and when included for present models, their contribution was generally feeble.

Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity: From 19 bioclimatic variables obtained from WorldClim, different variable combinations – chosen through expert knowledge of the biology of the system under study - were tested to choose the most informative and low-correlated (Pearson coefficient) set of variables.

Model settings

maxent: featureSet (Linear, Quadratic, Product and Hinge), regularizationMultiplierSet (Wild, Wild sl, Semiwild, Landrace datasets at 3. Commercial and Cultivated datasets at 1.), Jackknife (true), removeDuplicates (true), writeBackgroundPredictions (true), doClamp (true), randomSeed (true), convergenceThresholdSet (0.001), backgroundPoints (10,000), maximumIterations (5,000), randomTestPercentage (30), replicateType (cross validate), outputFormat (logistic)

Model settings (extrapolation): Clamping

Model estimates

Coefficients: median

Parameter uncertainty: No quantification of uncertainty.

Variable importance: Percent contribution and permutation importance

Model selection - model averaging - ensembles

Model selection: Combination of lowest corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc) values and high average test Area Under the Curve (AUC). Medium to low omission rates were considered acceptable.

Model averaging: Median

Model ensembles: None

Analysis and Correction of non-independence

Spatial autocorrelation: None

Temporal autocorrelation: None

Nested data: None

Threshold selection

Threshold selection: Upper 10th quantile value of the distribution of training values for each model was calculated independently. Thresholds on future projections were obtained from the present time models of each dataset.

Assessment

Performance statistics

Performance on training data: AUC, AIC

Performance on validation data: AIC, AUC, AUC difference, False negative rate, TSS, True negative rate

<Performance on test data>

Plausibility check

Response shapes: Response curves and mapped predictions inspection

Expert judgement: Mapped predictions

Prediction

Prediction output

Prediction unit: Mean and standard deviation of the 10 output grids per model

Post-processing: Projections were calculated and plotted for the custom-square clipped layers (present and future). These layers were cropped to a custom box chosen as informative of our study area plus southern United States, Central America and northern tip of South America. Future projections of replicates were averaged through medians and standard deviations obtained.

Uncertainty quantification

Algorithmic uncertainty: None

Input data uncertainty: None

Parameter uncertainty: None

Scenario uncertainty: None

Novel environments: Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces were visually inspected with emphasis on areas predicted to shift along future scenarios.